

Embedding voices of under-served communities in Health Research Priority Setting in Thailand

Facilitators' Guide

Napat Khirikoekong^a, Supa-at Asarath^a, Anne Osterrieder^{a,b}, Khin Maung Lwin^c, Phaik Yeong Cheah^{a,b*}

a Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit, Faculty of Tropical Medicine, Mahidol University, Bangkok, 10400 Thailand

b Nuffield Department of Medicine, Centre for Tropical Medicine and Global Health, University of Oxford, Oxford, OX3 7LG, UK

c Shoklo Malaria Research Unit, Mae Ramat, 63140 Thailand

Corresponding author email ID: phaikyeong@tropmedres.ac

Facilitators' Guide

Self-introduction of facilitator(s) and inform participants the purpose of today's activities

- We are here today to discuss with you, listen to you about health-related problems in your community now and in the near future
- We want to hear from you and understand the health burdens facing your community
- We may not/would not be able to solve these problems but discussing about it, but will help us understand your community's situation better
- There is no right or wrong answer
- We will take 2-3 hours, refreshments will be available

If ice-breaker is needed, allow the group to spend 10-15 minutes on ice-breaking activity.

1. Begin session with normal greetings in local languages by asking all participants following questions
 - How are you today?
 - How are you feeling?
 - Do you enjoy your meals these days?
 - If yes, tell us a bit more about it.
 - If no, tell us a bit more about it

Start a formal discussion on health by using below questions to guide the conversation/discussion

Part 1: How much do participants know, and how do they think of our research institute, and what we do

1. Do you know what a health research institute [name of research institute] does? Tell us a bit about what you know about [name of research institute]
2. Based on what you've heard or read or know, what do health researchers do? Can you tell us what health researchers do?
3. In your view, are there any health-related topic that we [name of research institute] should pay more attention and do something about? What is it?
 - a. Why should we [name of research institute] pay more attention and do something about it?

Part 2: Health burdens facing community

Use community mapping method. Can use drawing by participants to complement discussion or write down different groups of people on flipchart and add anything they said is faced by each specific group.

1. In the past 2-3 years, in your community/area, what are health problems/burden/challenges that people in your community face?
 - a. Who or which group suffered/impacted the most? How? tell us more about that...

Probes

- b. What are some health problems faced by small children?
- c. How do these health problems impact the lives of the children in your community?
- d. What are some health problems faced by young/teenagers/highschoolers?
- e. How do these health problems impact the lives of young/teenagers/highschoolers?
- f. What are some health problems faced by working adults?
- g. How do these health problems impact the lives of working adults?

- h. What are some health problems faced by older people?
- i. How do these health problems impact the lives of older people?
- j. Are there any unusual or new illness/health problems that you've heard of in your community?

Part 3: What action(s) are needed, by who and why?

1. With these health problems/challenges discussed, which one is the most important and that we need to do something to change it? Use scale for participants to discuss and provide table to rank the importance, the impact and the urgency for intervention.
 - a. What do you think needs to be done?
 - b. Who should be involved or do something about these health problems/challenges? Why do you think so?
 - c. Do we need to do study/research on it? Why?

Part 4.1: What research topic should we [name of research institute] do more to change/improve/benefit your health/health of your family members/community members in the future [next 5-10 years]?

Use flipchart and post-it notes for this discussion/exercise. Prepare flipchart and place on wall in venue with 3-4 four tables (depending on number of participants in the group: 1) topic/disease, 2) site/area, 3) potential participants, 4) benefits

Place post-it notes under each topic. Once all questioned are covered, reorganise post-it notes and clarify the relation from one table to the next.

Can ask participants to help with this exercise.

- a. What/which health topic/disease that need more research done?
[one topic/disease per note]
And why?
Probe:
 - i. how is such topic/disease affecting you/your community or any particular group of people?
[one group of people per note]
- b. Where [site/area] should such research topic be conducted?

[one site/area per note]

- c. Which group of participants/community members can potentially be involved in such research topic?

[one group per note]

- i. Probe: any specific group? E.g. patients? Age group?
- d. What kind of benefits would this new research topic offer for your health/health of your family members/community in the future?
 - i. How can we maximise benefits of research?

Part 4.2 What should we [name of research institute] consider when we think or plan to conduct new research topics?

Probe:

- ii. who should we ask/involve for new ideas/topic to conduct research on?
- iii. Why should we ask these people/group of people?

Optional/if deemed appropriate

- Are you interested to hear about research after it is finished?
- What is the best way for institute/study team to share/communicate research information with you/your community? Who can support us in this?
- What outcomes would you like to see from health research in the next 5-10 years?